

**Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part VII.
Some Anomalous Variations of Viscosity during
the Coagulation of Ferric Hydroxide and
Antimony Sulphide Sols.**

BY SHRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI AND A. S. NANJAPPA.

In previous parts of this series (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329 ; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 599) it was shown that an initial diminution followed by a rise of viscosity, and the existence of breaks in the viscosity—time curves were the conspicuous features of the *slow* coagulations of arsenious sulphide and gelatine sols (both when free and mixed together) in the presence of the solutions of a number of electrolytes, the strength of the sol and of the coagulator being varied over a suitable range in each series. Since the existence of both these phenomena has an important bearing both on the general theory of the viscosity of colloids and of the coagulation process, and since with the exception of the above work from these laboratories, practically no information is available in the literature in this line, it was thought desirable to extend the above results to coagulations of some other sols.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The method of measuring the viscosity and the general experimental procedure were the same as those adopted previously (*loc. cit.*). The values for the colloid and the coagulator concentration refer to those before mixing. The measurement of the viscosity was discontinued only after *flocculation* had set in. The temperature of the thermostat was kept constant at $35^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ in all the experiments. 30 C.c. of the coagulating mixture were used. It contained 20 c.c. of the sol and 10 c.c. of the appropriate electrolyte solution, except in No. 1, Table I, when 10 c.c. of water only were added to the colloid. All these liquids were allowed to attain the thermostat temperature before mixing in the viscometer. The constancy of the

pressure observed on the manometer (cf. Fig. A, Part V, Joshi and Viswanath, *loc. cit.*) applied to the viscometer was judged by means of a low power telescope.

During the course of preliminary experiments it was observed that a *freshly dried* viscometer always indicated a higher viscosity in the first observation. By examining this phenomenon under different conditions it was found that even with pure water the apparent viscosity in the initial observation could be as high as 2 % when the viscometer was highly desiccated by a prolonged current of hot and well dried air passed through it. This factor, however, could be eliminated by measuring the viscosity after the capillary and the bulb of the viscometer were once wetted by the liquid in the viscometer. In the following experiments, therefore, the viscometer was well wetted by the colloid before measurements of the viscosity of the coagulating mixture were commenced.

The kinetics of the coagulation of two colloids, *viz.*, ferric oxide and antimony sulphide were examined viscometrically and the results were similar to those in Part V (Joshi and Viswanath, *loc. cit.*). The ferric oxide sol was prepared by hydrolysing a solution containing about 5 g. of ferric chloride per litre by prolonged boiling and then dialysing it for 20 days. The dialysate was found to be free of chlorine after

FIG. 1. (cf. TABLE I).

Curve 1 refers to water and Fe_2O_3 sol. Curves 2—4 refer to Fe_2O_3 sol + 0.0002, 0.001 and 0.002 N-KCl respectively.

this period. The colloid content of the sol was determined by coagulating a known amount of the sol by a barium chloride solution and then weighing the coagulum. It was 1.95 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre. The viscosity variations during its coagulation by solutions of potassium chloride, barium chloride, ferric chloride and thorium nitrate are shown in Figs. 1—4 (cf. Tables I—IV). The antimony

FIG. 2. (cf. TABLE II).

Curves 5—10 refer to Fe_2O_3 sol + 0.0025, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05 and 0.1N- BaCl_2 respectively.

FIG. 3. (cf. TABLE III).

Curves 11—13 refer to Fe_2O_3 sol + 0.01, 0.02, and 0.1N- FeCl_3 respectively.

FIG. 4. (cf. TABLE IV).

Curves 14–15 refer to Fe_2O_3 sol + 0.1 and 1.0N- $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ respectively.

sulphide sol was prepared as in an earlier paper (Joshi and Prabhu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11). It was dialysed for 12 days against repeated changes of hot water and was found free of acid. A portion of this sol was diluted with water and used in the experiments with thorium nitrate (Fig. 8 also Table VIII). The other portion of the sol was dialysed for 14 days longer, and used in coagulations by solutions of potassium chloride, potassium tartrate and potassium oxalate (Figs. 5–7; Tables V–VII). The concentrations of these sols, determined as in the case of colloid ferric oxide, were respectively, 2.05 and 1.45 g. of Sb_2S_3 per litre. The data in the 4th column of Tables I–VIII show η , the viscosity in centipoise units at the first minimum observed on the η –time curves. The time corresponding to this minimum is shown in the next column. As observed previously, the η –time curves were discontinuous. In order to give an idea of the magnitude of these discontinuities only one pair of points, which are *widest* apart on the η -axis of each curve, is considered, e.g., points *a* and *b* on curve 2, Fig. 1. The mean of the difference between the viscosities corresponding to *a* and *b*, is expressed as a percentage of the *initial* viscosity. These results are given in the 9th column of Tables I–VIII.

The following abbreviations have been used in the following tables:

C = concentration of electrolytes; η_i = initial viscosity in centipoise; η_m = first minimum viscosity; $T\eta_m$ = time corresponding to η_m ; η_d = viscosity decrease; η_f = final observed viscosity; $T\eta_f$ = time corresponding to η_f ; R = range of fluctuation of η .

TABLE I (cf. Fig. 1).

Fe_2O_3 sol + water.

Ref. curve No.	C .	η_i .	η_m .	$T\eta_m$.	η_d .	η_f .	$T\eta_f$.	R .	Remarks.
1		0.717	0.713	45	0.6%	0.713	145		

Fe_2O_3 sol + KCl.

2	0.0002N	0.750	0.729	22	2.8%	0.738	120	0.4%	No flocculation.
3	0.0010	0.748	0.731	48	2.3	0.731	128	—	Do
4	0.0020	0.748	0.736	43	1.6	0.739	128	0.2	Flocculates.

TABLE II (cf. Fig. 2).

Fe_2O_3 sol + BaCl_2 .

5	0.0025N	0.736	0.719	35	2.3%	0.717	120	0.3%	No flocculation.
6	0.0050	0.726	0.717	30	1.2	0.716	121	0.2	Do
7	0.0100	0.735	0.727	30	1.1	0.731	132	0.2	Opalescent after 30'.
8	0.0200	0.737	0.721	60	2.2	0.720	98	0.6	Opalescent after 20'. Flocculates after 98'.
9	0.0500	0.751	0.720	44	4.1	0.719	104	0.2	Opalescent after 15'. Flocculates after 44'. Coagulates after 104'.
10	0.1000	0.751	0.725	25	3.5	0.725	98	0.3	Opalescent immediately. Flocculates after 48'. Coagulates completely after 88'.

TABLE III (cf. Fig. 3).

Fe_2O_3 sol + FeCl_3 .

11	0.01N	0.741	0.730	38	1.5%	0.730	213	0.1%	No flocculation.
12	0.05	0.741	0.721	62	2.7	0.720	140	—	Do
13	0.10	0.749	0.730	53	2.5	0.730	130	0.3	Opalescent after 39'. Flocculates after 97'.

TABLE IV (cf. Fig. 4).

 Fe_2O_3 sol + $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$.

Ref.	C.	η_i	η_m	$T\eta_m$	η_d	η_f	$T\eta_f$	R.	Remarks.
14	0.10N	0.809	0.721	25	10.9%	0.719	120	—	No flocculation.
15	1.00	0.819	0.770	45	6.0	0.768	102	0.2%	Opalescent immediately. Flocculates after 64'. Coagulates completely after 102'.

TABLE V (cf. Fig. 5).

 Sb_2S_3 sol + KCl.

1	0.001N	0.749	0.740	16	1.2%	0.760	116	—	No flocculation.
2	0.005	0.745	0.738	17	0.9	0.790	137	—	Do
3	0.010	0.756	0.741	26	2.0	0.834	126	1.3%	Do
4	0.020	0.752	...	...	...	0.851	125	0.6	Do
5	0.030	0.753	...	...	...	0.951	44	26.0	Opalescent after 24'. Flocculates after 44'.
6	0.050	0.764	...	...	...	1.190	39	53.0	Opalescent after 17'. Flocculates after 39'.

TABLE VI (cf. Fig. 6).

 Sb_2S_3 sol + $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$.

7	0.010N	0.760	0.737	24	3.0%	0.741	114	0.3%	No flocculation.
8	0.025	0.754	0.734	18	2.7	0.750	118	0.3	Do
9	0.040	0.757	0.743	35	1.9	0.753	125	1.7	Do
10	0.050	0.754	...	...	...	1.448	87	...	Opalescent after 48'. Flocculates after 87'.

TABLE VII (cf. Fig. 7).

 Sb_2S_3 sol + $\text{K}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$.

11	0.020N	0.742	0.728	25	1.9%	0.726	114	0.4%	No flocculation.
12	0.040	0.748	0.729	26	2.5	0.730	126	0.3	Do
13	0.050	0.752	...	...	...	0.821	129	...	Opalescent after 59'. Flocculates after 129'.
14	0.060	0.753	...	...	...	1.026	82	...	Opalescent after 24'. Flocculates after 70'.

TABLE VIII (cf. Fig. 8).

 Sb_2S_3 sol + $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$.

Ref.	C.	η_i .	η_m .	$T\eta_m$.	η_d .	η_f .	$T\eta_f$.	R.	Remarks.
15	0.001N	0.726	...	...	...	0.728	125	0.5%	No flocculation.
16	0.002	0.733	0.725	16	1.1%	0.732	116	0.3	Do
17	0.003	0.722	...	...	...	0.731	122	0.5	Do
18	0.004	0.731	0.725	61	0.8	0.727	129	0.3	Do
19	0.005	0.738	0.732	35	0.8	0.740	125	0.6	Do
20	0.006	0.739	...	...	...	0.760	161	1.0	Opalescent after 96' Flocculates after 122'.

FIG. 5 (cf. TABLE V).

Curves 1-4 refer to Sb_2S_3 sol + 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, and 0.05N-KCl respectively.

FIG. 6 (cf. TABLE VI).

Curves 7—10 refer to Sb_2S_3 sol + 0.01, 0.025, 0.04 and 0.05N- $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ respectively.

FIG. 7. (cf. TABLE VII).

Curves 11—14 refer to Sb_2S_3 sol + 0.02, 0.04, 0.05 and 0.06N $\text{K}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$ respectively.

FIG. 8. (cf. TABLE VIII).

Curves 15—20 refer to Sb_2S_3 sol + 0.001, 0.002, 0.003, 0.004, 0.005 and 0.006N- $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ respectively.

DISCUSSION.

An examination of the curves in Fig. 1—8 gives ample support to the deduction made previously (Parts V, VI) that in so far as the viscosity is a measure of coagulation, at least in the *slow* region, the coagulation (in the sense of a sustained coalescence of particles) is not a continuous process in respect of time. As has been observed previously (*loc. cit.*), in a number of cases, *e.g.*, curves 3—6 in Fig. 5, curves 12—14 in Fig. 7 are 'S-shaped' showing a slow initial change followed by a more rapid one. In general this is ascribed to *autocatalysis*. This is not strictly valid since the existence of discontinuities on η —time curves might also be interpreted as showing that a viscosity change is not a measure of coagulation. It is instructive to consider the influence of the electrolyte concentration revealed by the curves in Figs. 5 and 7 for the antimony sulphide sol. The S-shaped part of the curve becomes progressively steeper as the strength of the electrolyte solution is increased. Moreover, at very low values of the last, when practically the entire η —time curve is a part of the S-shape, there are hardly any marked discontinuities. These are more pronounced at higher concentrations (*cf.* curves 5, 6, Fig. 5), *wherewith only*, coagulation was observed to

progress' sensibly as judged by opalescence and the setting in of flocculation (cf. Table V). This shows clearly that the discontinuities are a part of the mechanism of the coagulation of polydisperse sols, at any rate in the *slow* region. It might also be pointed out that the almost constancy of the viscosity (subsequent to the initial stage) where coagulation was either nil (cf. curve 1, Fig. 1) or had a very low rate of progress (cf. curves 11—13, Fig. 7; curves 1—3, Fig. 6) shows that the breaks in such curves as 5 and 6 in Fig. 5, where coagulation was most rapid, cannot be ascribed to any experimental error. This source would also appear to be improbable in view of the fact that the η -fluctuations on these curves are as high as 26 and 53 % (cf. Table V). It was previously observed (Part VI) that breaks were rather more frequent in coagulations due to thorium nitrate than when other electrolytes were used. This agrees with our present results (cf. Fig. 8). Curves 15—18 in this figure do not show any appreciable net increase of viscosity. This is sensible in curves 19 and especially in 20 in Fig. 8. These represent the largest concentration of the electrolytes, viz., thorium nitrate in this series. That coagulation was just appreciable only in the last case is shown by the evidence of opalescence and flocculations (cf. Table VIII). Considering the overall trend of the curve, it is seen to be S-shaped and it has also discontinuities. This is markedly different from the curves in Figs. 5—7 corresponding to the use of other coagulants where for the same sol, the S-parts of the η -time curves are sensibly free from discontinuities. It would thus appear that in the *slow* region the occurrence and the extent of these discontinuities depend upon the nature both of the colloid and of coagulator, and very likely also on the stage of the coagulation. Compared with η -time curves obtained in Part V for different series of coagulations, the initial viscosity diminution and the subsequent section of the curves, now observed for the coagulations of the antimony sulphide sol, are less pronounced. This is mainly due to the different scale used in plotting the results. The initial viscosity diminution now observed varies in the range 0.8—3 % of the initial viscosity and it is produced during 16—61 minutes after the commencement of the coagulation (cf. Tables V—VIII). On comparison, it will be seen that these quantities are similar to those reported previously in Parts V and VI (*loc. cit.*).

An outstanding feature of the viscosity—time curves (Figs. 1—4) for the coagulation of the ferric hydroxide sol is that the change

is accompanied by a diminution of viscosity. This is contrary to the general experience, *viz.* that coagulation produces an increase in the viscosity of a sol. These curves (Figs. 1—4) also show that decrease of viscosity becomes more pronounced in the order $\text{KCl} < \text{BaCl}_2 < \text{FeCl}_3 < \text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$. It is interesting to consider the viscosity diminution at the first minimum in these η -time curves (*cf.* columns 6, Tables I—IV). This varies from 1-10 % of the initial viscosity, about 3 % being the average value. The time corresponding to this occurrence lies in the range of 20-60 minutes after the start of the coagulation. Work is now in progress in these laboratories to investigate as to how far this viscosity diminution is similar to that observed in the case of the coagulation of the antimony sulphide sol studied, here and of other sols referred to in Parts V and VI.

SUMMARY.

Slow coagulations of colloid ferric oxide due to variously concentrated KCl , BaCl_2 , FeCl_3 and $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ and of antimony sulphide by KCl , $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $\text{K}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$ and $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ solutions have been studied by measurement of the viscosity with time. As observed previously in parts V and VI, in a number of coagulations of the latter sol, the η -time curves show an initial fall of 0.8 to 3 % of initial viscosity during 16—61 minutes after the start of coagulation. The next section usually possesses 'S-shape' whose duration diminishes as the electrolyte concentration is increased. The η -time curves show a number of breaks which are considered to indicate that in the *slow* region the coagulation is not a time-continuous process. Contrary to the general experience of the coagulation phenomena, in the case of the Fe_2O_3 the coagulation was accompanied by a diminution of η , the effect increasing in the order, $\text{KCl} < \text{BaCl}_2 < \text{FeCl}_3 < \text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$.

